

Controlling SARS-COV 2 by triplet oxygen molecules, spinning bubbles and other spinors- a hypothesis

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Abstract: Up to date, several medical methods have been proposed to cure covid-19; however, some of these techniques are very expensive for non-developing countries. For this reason, it is needed to employ newest scientific techniques which be more cheapest. In this research, we suggest a spinor medical method in controlling this disease. In this model, we will use of spinning oxygen molecules to cancel harmful effects of spinning viruses. To open discussion, we should remember that SARS-COV2 causes to a decrease in needed oxygen molecules within the lung. There are several reasons for this event, however, we propose a new evidence which may be ignored. We suppose that hemoglobin molecules which contain iron atoms move along blood vessels around alveolus of lungs and change spins of ions, charges and biological molecules within or around alveolar cells. These spinning cells attract triplet oxygen molecules with opposite spins. For example, a cell with ($\downarrow\downarrow$) spins attract oxygen molecule with opposite spins ($O-O(\uparrow\uparrow)$). The same may occur for spinning viruses. Alveolar spinning cells (for example with $\downarrow\downarrow\dots$) select spinning viruses with opposite spins ($\uparrow\uparrow\dots$). On the other hand, these viruses could repel oxygen molecules with the parallel spins and cause to a decrease in needed oxygen for human's body. In this hypothesis, spins of biological cells for any person may be different. To cure spinning viral diseases, we can design a system from two connected vessels, one including water and oxygen molecules and other including viruses. Two sides of vessels are warm and their middles are cooled. We connect them to each other and close the vessel of viruses but open vessel of water molecules. During respirations, spinning oxygen and other molecules which come out of alveolus, interact with vessels and cause that anti-parallel spinors, oxygen molecules and viruses become close and parallel spins go away. These interactions cause that molecules move along vessels and some waves exchange between them. These spinor waves induce shape of spinning viruses within water and gas vessel and produce virtual viruses. These virtual viruses could be confined by water molecules, make some bubbles and go out from system. These bubbles move towards the face, enter into the lung and alveolus and interact with real viruses. Spins of these bubbles are in opposite with spins of real spins and absorb them. Consequently, some spinless bubbles are emerged which have no effect on cells. This model could be used also in building spinor masks. These masks are formed from viruses, water and oxygen molecules. During respirations, spinning oxygen molecules which go out of alveolus change the spins of molecules within the mask. Consequently, spinning viruses which could be selected by alveolar cells go away from the face and become close to other end of mask. These viruses repel similar spinning viruses and prevent of their absorbing by mouth and nose. We formulate the model and obtain the needed current of oxygen molecules and bubbles to induce virtual viruses around real viruses within alveolus.

Keywords: Spining Virus; Spinor Mask; Alveolus; Bubbles; Triplet oxygen Molecules

I.Introduction:

In last decades, human confronts with wonderful diseases like different types of cancers and viruses. Although, technology helps to cure many of these diseases; however, it seems that some of them need to more progress in medical knowledge. For example, to prevent of spreading microbial diseases, some vaccines have been introduced and some drugs have been suggested. However, some of these medical methods are expensive specially for non-developing countries and providing and buying vaccines and drugs are very hard. For this reason, we should find some more simplest methods to cure and control these diseases. One of main diseases which all try to find cheapest medical methods for its curing is coronavirus disease 2019 (covid-19). This diseases is emerged by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). The first known case was identified in Wuhan, China, in December 2019 . Then, it has spread worldwide and cause to an ongoing pandemic [1-4]. Recently, several types of vaccines have been proposed which companies claiming their good actions against SARS-CoV-2. Some COVID-19 vaccines like the Pfizer–BioNTech and Moderna vaccines have been designed to apply RNA for stimulating the immune responses. When introduced into human tissue, the vaccine contains either self-replicating RNA or messenger RNA (mRNA), which both cause cells to express the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein. This teaches the body how to identify and destroy the corresponding pathogen [5-7]. Some other types of vaccines like the Sputnik V COVID-19 vaccine use an adenovirus shell containing DNA that encodes a SARS-CoV-2 protein. The viral vector-based vaccines against COVID-19 are non-replicating, meaning that they do not make new virus particles, but rather produce only the antigen which elicits a systemic immune response [8]. Also, there are some inactivated vaccines which consist of virus particles. These particles are grown in culture and then killed using a method such as heat or formaldehyde to lose disease producing capacity, while still stimulating an immune response [9]. Besides vaccines, some drugs have suggested which may be helpful in curing COVID-19 disease. For example, some antiviral medications like Molnupiravir inhibit the replication of certain RNA viruses, and are used to treat COVID-19 in those infected by SARS-CoV-2 [10]. Or some drugs like Nirmatrelvir which is an antiviral medication developed by Pfizer and act as 3CL protease inhibitor [11]. And also some drugs use of antibodies against SARS-COV-2 [12]. Some of these drugs are expensive and many people couldn't provide them easily. For this reason, we should explore more better medical cures. To this aim, we can use of some physical concepts in controlling spins. Specially in the case of SARS-COV-2, there are some hopes which they use of spinor waves in exchanging information. For example, it seems that by entering these viruses into alveolus, triplet oxygen molecules go out from it. Maybe, these viruses produce some spinor states which repel parallel states like triplet states of oxygen molecules. If this hypothesis be true, we can use of quantum principles in controlling covid-19 disease.

II. The Model: Spinor curing methods and spinor masks against SARS-COV 2

In this section, we suggest a model for controlling spinning viruses by using spinning biological molecules like triplet oxygen molecules or viruses with opposite spins. In this model:

1. We use of this fact that parallel spins repel each other and anti-parallel spins attract each other. The velocity of exchanging information between spins is more than the velocity of light. For example, in a pair of two anti-parallel spins, when the arrow of one spin changes, the arrow of ther spin could change immediately (See Figure 1).
2. It has been known that the stable spinor state of an oxygen molecule (O-O) is a triplet. A triplet oxygen includes at least two parallel spinors like two parallel electrons.
3. Triple oxygen molecules (O-O($\uparrow\uparrow$)) could attract triplet oxygen molecules with opposite directions ((O-O($\downarrow\downarrow$))). Also these molecules repel oxygen molecules with the same spins (O-O($\uparrow\uparrow$)) (See Figure 1).
4. Within each alveolus of lung, there are several types of cells like AT I which help in exchanging oxygen and carbon gases with blood cells and also AT II and macrophages which have different actions (See Figure 2).
5. Around each alveolus, there are some blood vessels which red blood cells including hemoglobin move along them (See Figure 2).
6. Hemoglobin contains iron atoms and could take spinning states and induce them to spinors within alveolar ells and ions around them (See Figure 2).
7. Spining alveolar cells could attract only one type of oxygen molecules with opposite spins and repel spinning molecules with parallel spins (See Figure 2).
8. Alveolar cells could also attract spinning viruses with opposite spins. Spins of these viruses are in parallel with spins of oxygens and consequently repel them. This causes that needed oxygen molecules within an alveolus decrease (See Figure 3).
9. To cure spinning viral diseases, we provide two vessels, one including water molecules and oxygen gases and other including spinning viruses (See Figure 4).
10. We put two vessels near each other and connect them to a heater-cooler system. Two ends of vessels should be warm and middle of them should be cooled (See Figure 4).
11. We bring this system near the face of patients. Spining oxygen molecules collide with vessels and induce reverse spins to water and oxygen molecules within vessels (See Figure 4).
12. Spining viruses with opposite spins become closed and other viruses with the same spins go away (See Figure 4).
13. By changing temperature along vessels, spinors move and take the shape of viruses. Consequently, within water vessel, some virtual viruses are emerged. Spins of these viruses are in opposite with spins of real viruses within person's body (See Figure 4).
14. Virtual viruses are confined within water bubbles and eventually evaporate and enter into the body and alveolus (See Figure 4).

Figure 2: Hemoglobin induces special spins on cellular membranes and spinors around them within an alveolus. These spinning cells choose oxygen molecules with opposite spins- A hypothesis

Figure 3: Viruses with opposite spins respect to cells could be attracted by them. Also, these viruses repel all oxygen molecules with the same spins.

Figure 4: A model for inducing virtual viruses around cells within alveolus to combine with real viruses with opposite spins and cancel their effects

Figure 5: A model for spinor mask which could be built by viral vaccines, water and spinning oxygen molecules

III. The Mathematical Results:

In this section, we formulate the model and obtain the current of bubbles and oxygen molecules which emit needed waves for inducing virtual viruses around real viruses within lung. These virtual particles cancel the real viral effects and control viral diseases. To begin discussion, we suppose that each steam plane of bubbles has a total spin. Each steam plane is formed from several numbers of sheets. Total spin of a steam system could be obtained from below equation:

$$S_{\text{Steam}} \rightarrow \sum_j n_{\text{sheet},j} S_{\text{sheet},j}$$

(1)

Where S_{Steam} is total spin of a steam system, $n_{\text{sheet},j}$ is the number of sheets, j is the number of sheets and $S_{\text{sheet},j}$ is the spin of sheets. Spin of each sheet could be obtained from below equation:

$$S_{\text{sheet},j} \rightarrow \sum_i n_{\text{bubble},ij} S_{\text{bubble},ij} \quad (2)$$

Where $n_{\text{bubble},ij}$ is the number of bubbles, $S_{\text{bubble},ij}$ is the spin of bubbles and i,j are related indices. Each bubble can contain several gas molecules like triplet O_2 . Thus, total spin of a bubble molecule could be obtained from below equation:

$$S_{\text{bubble},ij} \rightarrow \sum_k n_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} S_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} + \sum_l n_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} S_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} \quad (3)$$

Where $n_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk}$ and $n_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl}$ are number of free electrons and holes. Also, ijk are related indices and $S_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk}$ and $S_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl}$ are spins of free electrons and holes. Substituting results of equations (2,3) in equation (1) gives:

$$S_{\text{Steam}} \rightarrow \sum_j n_{\text{sheet},j} \sum_i n_{\text{bubble},ij} [\sum_k n_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} S_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} + \sum_l n_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} S_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl}] \quad (4)$$

Using above result, we can obtain the below energy density:

$$U_{\text{Steam}} \rightarrow \frac{[\hbar \mathcal{N}' S_{\text{Steam}}]^2}{2 \mu_0}$$

$$\mathcal{N}' \rightarrow \frac{e}{2 m \hbar} \quad (e, m, \hbar, c \dots)$$

(5)

Where \hbar is the plank constant, S_{Steam} is the steam spin, μ_0 is the magnetic constant and \mathcal{N}' is a constant depending on mass and electric charges. Substituting energy density of equation (4) in equation (5) gives:

$$U_{\text{Steam}} \rightarrow \frac{[\hbar \mathcal{N}']^2}{2 \mu_0} [\sum_j n_{\text{sheet},j} \sum_i n_{\text{bubble},ij} [\sum_k n_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} S_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} + \sum_l n_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} S_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl}]]^2 \quad (6)$$

Using above energy density, we can obtain total energy of a steam:

$$E_{\text{Steam}} = U_{\text{Steam}} V_{\text{Steam}} \quad (7)$$

Where V_{Steam} is the volume of a steam system and could be obtained from below equation:

$$V_{\text{Steam}} = 2\pi [\sum_j n_{\text{sheet},j} \sum_i n_{\text{bubble},ij} [R_{\text{bubble},ij} + x]] [\sum_j n_{\text{sheet},j} [L_{\text{sheet-sheet},j} + x]] \quad (8)$$

Where $L_{\text{sheet-sheet},j}$ is the steam sheet length, x is the size of vibration and $R_{\text{bubble},ij}$ is the radius of bubble molecule. Substituting results of equations (6 and 8) in equation (7) gives:

$$E_{\text{Steam}} \rightarrow \frac{\mathcal{N}'[\hbar]^2}{2 \mu_0} [\sum_j n_{\text{sheet},j} \sum_i n_{\text{bubble},ij} [\sum_k n_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} S_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} + \sum_l n_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} S_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl}]]^2 \otimes 2\pi [\sum_j n_{\text{sheet},j} \sum_i n_{\text{bubble},ij} [R_{\text{bubble},ij} + x]] [\sum_j n_{\text{sheet},j} [L_{\text{sheet-sheet},j} + x]]$$

(9)

Above equation corresponds to two coupled sheets. However, by separating two sheets, some extra spinors could enter into this system and produce some noises in entangled paired. For example, suppose that we have two entangled spinors at first:

$$|\uparrow\uparrow\rangle \text{ or } |\downarrow\downarrow\rangle \quad (10)$$

Then, each of these spinors could produce several thermal entanglements with extra spinors in medium [13,14]:

$$|\uparrow\uparrow, \text{initial}\rangle \rightarrow [\cos\alpha \Sigma_{n=0,1} \tan^n \alpha |\uparrow, n\rangle_{+1} | \downarrow, n\rangle_{-1}] \times [\cos\beta \Sigma_{m=0,1} \tan^m \beta |\uparrow, m\rangle_{+1} | \downarrow, m\rangle_{-1}] \quad (11)$$

where

$$\tan\alpha \approx \exp\left(-\frac{\pi E_{\text{noise, spinor-entanglement,}\uparrow}}{T_{\text{spinor-entanglement,}\uparrow}}\right)$$

$$\tan\beta \approx \exp\left(-\frac{\pi E_{\text{noise, spinor-entanglement,}\downarrow}}{T_{\text{spinor-entanglement,}\downarrow}}\right) \quad (12)$$

And

$$\mathbf{E}_{\text{noise, spinor-entanglement}} \rightarrow \frac{[\hbar]^2 S_{\text{noise, spin1}} S_{\text{noise, spin2}}}{2 \mu_0} \quad (13)$$

Substituting results of equation (11) in equation (9) yields:

$$\begin{aligned}
& E_{\text{Steam}} \rightarrow \\
& \frac{[\mathcal{N}'\hbar]^2}{2\mu_0} [\Sigma_j n_{\text{sheet},j} \Sigma_i n_{\text{bubble},ij} [\Sigma_k n_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} S_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} + \Sigma_l n_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} S_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl}]] \\
& \otimes [\prod_{z=1..n} \cos\alpha_{1,\text{noise}} \dots \cos\alpha_{w,\text{noise}}] \times \\
& \otimes [\Sigma_{f_1=0,1} \tan^{f_1} \alpha_{1,\text{noise}}] \dots [\Sigma_{f=0,1} \tan^f \alpha_{w,\text{noise}}] \\
& \frac{\otimes \mathcal{N}'[\hbar]^2}{2\mu_0} [\Sigma_m n_{\text{sheet},m} \Sigma_n n_{\text{bubble},mn} [\Sigma_x n_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} S'_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} + \Sigma_y n_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny} S'_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny}]] \\
& \otimes [2\pi [\Sigma_j n_{\text{sheet},j} \Sigma_i n_{\text{bubble},ij} [R_{\text{bubble},ij} + x]] [\Sigma_j n_{\text{sheet},j} [L_{\text{sheet-sheet},j} + x]]] \\
& + 2\pi [\Sigma_m n_{\text{sheet},m} \Sigma_i n_{\text{bubble},nm} [R'_{\text{bubble},nm} + x]] [\Sigma_m n_{\text{sheet},m} [L'_{\text{sheet-sheet},n} + x]] \\
& \otimes H_{\text{Separation Distance}}
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Where $H_{\text{Separation Distance}}$ is the separation distance between coupled steam sheets. By taking derivative of above equation with respect to x , one obtains:

$$F_{\text{Steam}} = \frac{d E_{\text{Steam}}}{dx} = K_{\text{Steam}} x + \text{constant} \tag{15}$$

Where

$$K_{\text{Steam}} = [2\pi [\Sigma_j n_{\text{sheet},j} \Sigma_i n_{\text{bubble},ij}] [\Sigma_j n_{\text{sheet},j}]]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& +2\pi [\Sigma_m n_{sheet,m} \Sigma_i n_{bubble,nm}] [\Sigma_m n_{sheet,m}] \\
& \frac{\otimes [\mathcal{N}'\hbar]^2}{2 \mu_0} [\Sigma_j n_{sheet,j} \Sigma_i n_{bubble,ij} [\Sigma_k n_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} S_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} + \Sigma_l n_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} S_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl}]] \\
& \otimes [\prod_{z=1..n} \cos\alpha_{1,noise} \dots \cos\alpha_{w,noise}] \times \\
& \otimes [\Sigma_{f_1=0,1} \tan^{f_1} \alpha_{1,noise}] \dots [\Sigma_{f=0,1} \tan^f \alpha_{w,noise}] \\
& \frac{\otimes [\mathcal{N}'\hbar]^2}{2 \mu_0} [\Sigma_m n_{sheet,m} \Sigma_n n_{bubble,mn} [\Sigma_x n_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} S'_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} + \Sigma_y n_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny} S'_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny}]] \\
& \otimes H_{Separation Distance}
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

For above equations, frequencies could be obtained from below equations.

$$\begin{aligned}
V_{Exchanged\ wave,\ sheet} &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \left[\frac{K_{Steam}}{M_{electron}} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \rightarrow \\
& \frac{1}{2\pi} \left[\frac{1}{M_{Tot,electron}} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} [[2\pi [\Sigma_j n_{sheet,j} \Sigma_i n_{bubble,ij}] [\Sigma_j n_{sheet,j}]] \\
& +2\pi [\Sigma_m n_{sheet,m} \Sigma_i n_{bubble,nm}] [\Sigma_m n_{sheet,m}] \\
& \frac{\otimes [\mathcal{N}'\hbar]^2}{2 \mu_0} [\Sigma_j n_{sheet,j} \Sigma_i n_{bubble,ij} [\Sigma_k n_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} S_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} + \Sigma_l n_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} S_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl}]] \\
& \otimes [\prod_{z=1..n} \cos\alpha_{1,noise} \dots \cos\alpha_{w,noise}] \times \\
& \otimes [\Sigma_{f_1=0,1} \tan^{f_1} \alpha_{1,noise}] \dots [\Sigma_{f=0,1} \tan^f \alpha_{w,noise}] \\
& \frac{\otimes [\mathcal{N}'\hbar]^2}{2 \mu_0} [\Sigma_m n_{sheet,m} \Sigma_n n_{bubble,mn} [\Sigma_x n_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} S'_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} + \Sigma_y n_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny} S'_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny}]] \\
& \otimes H_{Separation Distance}^{1/2}
\end{aligned}$$

(17)

Where

$$\begin{aligned}
 & M_{Tot,electron} \rightarrow \\
 & [\sum_j n_{sheet,j} \sum_i n_{bubble,ij} [\sum_k n_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} m_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} + \sum_l n_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} m_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl}]] \\
 & + [\sum_m n_{sheet,m} \sum_n n_{bubble,mn} [\sum_x n_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} m'_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} + \sum_y n_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny} m'_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny}]] + m_{noise}
 \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

Substituting result of equation (18) in equation (17) yields:

$$\begin{aligned}
 v_{Exchanged\ wave, sheet} &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \left[\frac{K_{Steam}}{M_{electron}} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \rightarrow \\
 & \frac{1}{2\pi} \\
 & \otimes [[\sum_j n_{sheet,j} \sum_i n_{bubble,ij} [\sum_k n_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} m_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} + \sum_l n_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} m_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl}]] \\
 & + [\sum_m n_{sheet,m} \sum_n n_{bubble,mn} [\sum_x n_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} m'_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} \\
 & + \sum_y n_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny} m'_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny}]] + m_{noise}]^{\frac{-1}{2}} \\
 & \otimes [[2\pi [\sum_j n_{sheet,j} \sum_i n_{bubble,ij}]] [\sum_j n_{sheet,j}] \\
 & + 2\pi [\sum_m n_{sheet,m} \sum_i n_{bubble,im}] [\sum_m n_{sheet,m}] \\
 & \frac{\otimes [N/\hbar]^2}{2\mu_0} [\sum_j n_{sheet,j} \sum_i n_{bubble,ij} [\sum_k n_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} S_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} + \sum_l n_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} S_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl}]]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \otimes [\prod_{z=1..n} \cos \alpha_{1,noise} \dots \cos \alpha_{w,noise}] \times \\
& \otimes [\Sigma_{f_1=0,1} \tan^{f_1} \alpha_{1,noise}] \dots [\Sigma_{f=0,1} \tan^f \alpha_{w,noise}] \\
& \frac{\otimes [\mathcal{N}'\hbar]^2}{2 \mu_0} [\Sigma_m n_{sheet,m} \Sigma_n n_{bubble,mn} [\Sigma_x n_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} S'_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} + \Sigma_y n_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny} S'_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny}]] \\
& \otimes [H_{Separation Distance}]^{1/2}
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

Above frequency corresponds to exchanged waves between steam sheets. However, it ignores the role of radiated spinors from biological cells. A cell could emit some spinors which fill holes or produce some new holes within steam system. For a normal cell, we can write the below frequency:

$$\begin{aligned}
V_{Exchanged\ wave, sheet, normal\ cell} &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \left[\frac{K_{Steam}}{M_{electron}} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \rightarrow \\
& \frac{1}{2\pi} \\
& \otimes [[\Sigma_j n_{sheet,j} \Sigma_i n_{bubble,ij} [\Sigma_k n_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} [m_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} - m_{radiated(\uparrow\uparrow),normal\ cell,ijk}] \\
& + \Sigma_i n_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} [m_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} - m_{radiated(\downarrow\downarrow),normal\ cell,,ijl}]]] \\
& + [\Sigma_m n_{sheet,m} \Sigma_n n_{bubble,mn} [\Sigma_x n_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} [m'_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} - m'_{radiated(\uparrow\uparrow),normal\ cell,mnx}] \\
& + \Sigma_y n_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny} [m'_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny} - m'_{radiated(\downarrow\downarrow),normal\ cell,mny}]]] + m_{noise}]^{\frac{-1}{2}} \\
& \otimes [[2\pi [\Sigma_j n_{sheet,j} \Sigma_i n_{bubble,ij}] [\Sigma_j n_{sheet,j}]]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 2\pi [\sum_m \mathbf{n}_{sheet,m} \sum_i \mathbf{n}_{bubble,nm}] [\sum_m \mathbf{n}_{sheet,m}] \\
& \otimes \frac{[\mathcal{N}\hbar]^2}{2\mu_0} [\sum_j \mathbf{n}_{sheet,j} \sum_i \mathbf{n}_{bubble,ij} [\sum_k [\mathbf{n}_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} \mathbf{S}_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} \\
& - \mathbf{n}_{radiated(\uparrow\uparrow),normal\ cell,ijk} \mathbf{S}_{radiated(\uparrow\uparrow),normal\ cell,ijk}] \\
& + \sum_l [\mathbf{n}_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} \mathbf{S}_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} - \mathbf{n}_{radiated(\downarrow\downarrow),normal\ cell,,ijl} \mathbf{S}_{radiated(\downarrow\downarrow),normal\ cell,,ijl}]] \\
& \otimes [\prod_{z=1..n} \cos\alpha_{1,noise} \dots \cos\alpha_{w,noise}] \times \\
& \otimes [\sum_{f_1=0,1} \tan^{f_1} \alpha_{1,noise}] \dots [\sum_{f=0,1} \tan^f \alpha_{w,noise}] \\
& \otimes \frac{[\mathcal{N}\hbar]^2}{2\mu_0} [\sum_m \mathbf{n}_{sheet,m} \sum_n \mathbf{n}_{bubble,mn} \\
& \otimes [\sum_x [\mathbf{n}_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} \mathbf{S}'_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} - \mathbf{n}_{radiated(\uparrow\uparrow),normal\ cell,,mnx} \mathbf{S}'_{radiated(\uparrow\uparrow),normal\ cell,,mnx}] \\
& + \sum_y [\mathbf{n}_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny} \mathbf{S}'_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny} - \mathbf{n}_{radiated(\downarrow\downarrow),normal\ cell,mny} \mathbf{S}'_{radiated(\downarrow\downarrow),normal\ cell,mny}]] \\
& \otimes [H_{Separation\ Distance}]^{1/2}
\end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Above frequency corresponds to exchanged waves between two sheets, one coming from interior of human's body near the human cells within lung and other coming from water exterior it. According to observations, viruses cause that cells emit different numbers of spinors and holes and radiated waves have below frequency:

$$\nu_{Exchanged\ wave,sheet, (virus-cell)} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \left[\frac{K_{Steam}}{M_{electron}} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \rightarrow$$

$$\frac{1}{2\pi}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \otimes [[\Sigma_j n_{sheet,j} \Sigma_i n_{bubble,ij} [\Sigma_k n_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} [\mathbf{m}_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} - \mathbf{m}_{radiated(\uparrow\uparrow), (virus-cell),ijk}] \\
& \quad + \Sigma_i n_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} [\mathbf{m}_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} - \mathbf{m}_{radiated(\downarrow\downarrow), (virus-cell),,ijl}]]]] \\
& + [\Sigma_m n_{sheet,m} \Sigma_n n_{bubble,mn} [\Sigma_x n_{\uparrow\uparrow, mnx} [\mathbf{m}'_{\uparrow\uparrow, mnx} - \mathbf{m}'_{radiated(\uparrow\uparrow), (virus-cell), mnx}] \\
& \quad + \Sigma_y n_{\downarrow\downarrow, mny} [\mathbf{m}'_{\downarrow\downarrow, mny} - \mathbf{m}'_{radiated(\downarrow\downarrow), (virus-cell), mny}]]] + \mathbf{m}_{noise}]^{\frac{-1}{2}} \\
& \quad \otimes [[2\pi [\Sigma_j n_{sheet,j} \Sigma_i n_{bubble,ij}] [\Sigma_j n_{sheet,j}] \\
& \quad + 2\pi [\Sigma_m n_{sheet,m} \Sigma_i n_{bubble,im}] [\Sigma_m n_{sheet,m}]] \\
& \quad \frac{\otimes [\mathcal{N}\hbar]^2}{2\mu_0} [\Sigma_j n_{sheet,j} \Sigma_i n_{bubble,ij} [\Sigma_k [n_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} \mathbf{S}_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} \\
& \quad - n_{radiated(\uparrow\uparrow), (virus-cell),ijk} \mathbf{S}_{radiated(\uparrow\uparrow), (virus-cell),ijk}] \\
& \quad + \Sigma_l [n_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} \mathbf{S}_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} - n_{radiated(\downarrow\downarrow), (virus-cell),,ijl} \mathbf{S}_{radiated(\downarrow\downarrow), (virus-cell),,ijl}]]]] \\
& \quad \otimes [\prod_{z=1..n} \cos\alpha_{1,noise} \dots \cos\alpha_{w,noise}] \times \\
& \quad \otimes [\Sigma_{f_1=0,1} \tan^{f_1} \alpha_{1,noise}] \dots [\Sigma_{f_w=0,1} \tan^{f_w} \alpha_{w,noise}] \\
& \quad \frac{\otimes [\mathcal{N}\hbar]^2}{2\mu_0} [\Sigma_m n_{sheet,m} \Sigma_n n_{bubble,mn} \\
& \quad \otimes [\Sigma_x [n_{\uparrow\uparrow, mnx} \mathbf{S}'_{\uparrow\uparrow, mnx} - n_{radiated(\uparrow\uparrow), (virus-cell),, mnx} \mathbf{S}'_{radiated(\uparrow\uparrow), (virus-cell),, mnx}] \\
& \quad + \Sigma_y [n_{\downarrow\downarrow, mny} \mathbf{S}'_{\downarrow\downarrow, mny} - n_{radiated(\downarrow\downarrow), (virus-cell), mny} \mathbf{S}'_{radiated(\downarrow\downarrow), (virus-cell), mny}]]]] \\
& \quad \otimes [H_{Separation Distance}]^{1/2}
\end{aligned}$$

(21)

Comparing equations (20 and 21), we find that (virus-cell)s emit waves with different frequencies with respect to normal cells. Thus, by considering exchanged waves between steam sheets\, one can diagnose (virus-cell)s.

Now, the question arises that how we can induce virtual Viruses around a cell? To answer this question, we should regard effects of viral charges on steam sheet holes and spinors. We can obtain the below frequency:

$$V_{\text{induced Virus}} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \left[\frac{K_{\text{Steam}}}{M_{\text{electron}}} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \rightarrow$$

$$\frac{1}{2\pi}$$

$$\otimes \left[\left[\sum_j n_{\text{sheet},j} \sum_i n_{\text{bubble},ij} \left[\sum_k n_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} \right. \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. \left. \otimes \left[m_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} - m_{\text{radiated}(\uparrow\uparrow),(\text{virus-cell}),ijk} + m_{\text{radiated}(\uparrow\uparrow),\text{induced Virus},ijk} \right] \right. \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. \left. + \sum_l n_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} \right. \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. \left. \otimes \left[m_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} - m_{\text{radiated}(\downarrow\downarrow),(\text{virus-cell}),ijl} + m_{\text{radiated}(\downarrow\downarrow),\text{induced Virus},ijl} \right] \right. \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. \left. + \left[\sum_m n_{\text{sheet},m} \sum_n n_{\text{bubble},mn} \left[\sum_x n_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} \right. \right. \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. \left. \otimes \left[m'_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} - m'_{\text{radiated}(\uparrow\uparrow),(\text{virus-cell}),mnx} + m'_{\text{radiated}(\uparrow\uparrow),\text{induced Virus},mnx} \right] \right. \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. \left. + \sum_y n_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny} \right. \right. \right.$$

$$\left. \left. \left. \otimes \left[m'_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny} - m'_{\text{radiated}(\downarrow\downarrow),(\text{virus-cell}),mny} + m'_{\text{radiated}(\downarrow\downarrow),\text{induced Virus},mny} \right] \right. \right. \right. + m_{\text{noise}} \left. \right]^{\frac{-1}{2}}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \otimes [[2\pi [\Sigma_j \mathbf{n}_{\text{sheet},j} \Sigma_i \mathbf{n}_{\text{bubble},ij}] [\Sigma_j \mathbf{n}_{\text{sheet},j}] \\
& + 2\pi [\Sigma_m \mathbf{n}_{\text{sheet},m} \Sigma_i \mathbf{n}_{\text{bubble},nm}] [\Sigma_m \mathbf{n}_{\text{sheet},m}] \\
& \frac{\otimes [\mathcal{N}\hbar]^2}{2\mu_0} [\Sigma_j \mathbf{n}_{\text{sheet},j} \Sigma_i \mathbf{n}_{\text{bubble},ij} [\Sigma_k [\mathbf{n}_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} \mathbf{S}_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} \\
& - \mathbf{n}_{\text{radiated}(\uparrow\uparrow),(\text{virus-cell}),ijk} \mathbf{S}_{\text{radiated}(\uparrow\uparrow),(\text{virus-cell}),ijk} \\
& + \mathbf{n}_{\text{radiated}(\uparrow\uparrow),\text{induced Virus},ijk} \mathbf{S}_{\text{radiated}(\uparrow\uparrow),\text{induced Virus},ijk}] \\
& + \Sigma_l [\mathbf{n}_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} \mathbf{S}_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} \\
& - \mathbf{n}_{\text{radiated}(\downarrow\downarrow),(\text{virus-cell}),ijl} \mathbf{S}_{\text{radiated}(\downarrow\downarrow),(\text{virus-cell}),ijl} \\
& + \mathbf{n}_{\text{radiated}(\downarrow\downarrow),\text{induced Virus},ijl} \mathbf{S}_{\text{radiated}(\downarrow\downarrow),\text{induced Virus},ijl}]] \\
& \otimes [[\prod_{z=1..n} \cos\alpha_{1,\text{noise}} \dots \cos\alpha_{w,\text{noise}}] \times \\
& \otimes [\Sigma_{f_1=0,1} \tan^{f_1} \alpha_{1,\text{noise}}] \dots [\Sigma_{f=0,1} \tan^f \alpha_{w,\text{noise}}] \\
& \frac{\otimes [\mathcal{N}\hbar]^2}{2\mu_0} [\Sigma_m \mathbf{n}_{\text{sheet},m} \Sigma_n \mathbf{n}_{\text{bubble},mn} \\
& \otimes [\Sigma_x [\mathbf{n}_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} \mathbf{S}'_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} \\
& - \mathbf{n}_{\text{radiated}(\uparrow\uparrow),(\text{virus-cell}),,mnx} \mathbf{S}'_{\text{radiated}(\uparrow\uparrow),(\text{virus-cell}),,mnx} \\
& + \mathbf{n}_{\text{radiated}(\uparrow\uparrow),\text{induced Virus},,mnx} \mathbf{S}'_{\text{radiated}(\uparrow\uparrow),\text{induced Virus},,mnx}] \\
& + \Sigma_y [\mathbf{n}_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny} \mathbf{S}'_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny} \\
& - \mathbf{n}_{\text{radiated}(\downarrow\downarrow),(\text{virus-cell}),mny} \mathbf{S}'_{\text{radiated}(\downarrow\downarrow),(\text{virus-cell}),mny} \\
& + \mathbf{n}_{\text{radiated}(\downarrow\downarrow),\text{induced Virus},mny} \mathbf{S}'_{\text{radiated}(\downarrow\downarrow),\text{induced Virus},mny}]]]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\otimes [H_{\text{Separation Distance}}]^{1/2}$$

(22)

This frequency corresponds to waves which induce Viruses around (virus-cell)s. This frequency cause to motions of charges and their velocity which could be obtained from below equation:

$$V_{\text{Virus-cell,bubbles}} = L_{\text{sheet-sheet}} [2\pi v_{\text{induced Virus}}] \rightarrow$$

$$L_{\text{sheet-sheet}} [[\Sigma_j n_{\text{sheet},j} \Sigma_i n_{\text{bubble},ij} [\Sigma_k n_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk}$$

$$\otimes [m_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} - m_{\text{radiated}(\uparrow\uparrow),(\text{virus-cell}),ijk} + m_{\text{radiated}(\uparrow\uparrow),\text{induced Virus},ijk}]$$

$$+ \Sigma_l n_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl}]$$

$$\otimes [m_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} - m_{\text{radiated}(\downarrow\downarrow),(\text{virus-cell}),ijl} + m_{\text{radiated}(\downarrow\downarrow),\text{induced Virus},ijl}]]$$

$$+ [\Sigma_m n_{\text{sheet},m} \Sigma_n n_{\text{bubble},mn} [\Sigma_x n_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx}$$

$$\otimes [m'_{\uparrow\uparrow,mnx} - m'_{\text{radiated}(\uparrow\uparrow),(\text{virus-cell}),mnx} + m'_{\text{radiated}(\uparrow\uparrow),\text{induced Virus},mnx}]$$

$$+ \Sigma_y n_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny}]$$

$$\otimes [m'_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny} - m'_{\text{radiated}(\downarrow\downarrow),(\text{virus-cell}),mny} + m'_{\text{radiated}(\downarrow\downarrow),\text{induced Virus},mny}]] + m_{\text{noise}}]^{-1/2}$$

$$\otimes [[2\pi [\Sigma_j n_{\text{sheet},j} \Sigma_i n_{\text{bubble},ij}] [\Sigma_j n_{\text{sheet},j}]$$

$$+ 2\pi [\Sigma_m n_{\text{sheet},m} \Sigma_i n_{\text{bubble},im}] [\Sigma_m n_{\text{sheet},m}]]$$

$$\frac{\otimes [N\hbar]^2}{2\mu_0} [\Sigma_j n_{\text{sheet},j} \Sigma_i n_{\text{bubble},ij} [\Sigma_k [n_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} S_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk}$$

$$- n_{\text{radiated}(\uparrow\uparrow),(\text{virus-cell}),ijk} S_{\text{radiated}(\uparrow\uparrow),(\text{virus-cell}),ijk}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \mathbf{n}_{\text{radiated}}(\uparrow\uparrow), \text{ induced Virus,ijk} \mathbf{S}_{\text{radiated}}(\uparrow\uparrow), \text{ induced Virus,ijk}] \\
& \quad + \Sigma_l [\mathbf{n}_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} \mathbf{S}_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} \\
& \quad - \mathbf{n}_{\text{radiated}}(\downarrow\downarrow), (\text{virus-cell}),,ijl} \mathbf{S}_{\text{radiated}}(\downarrow\downarrow), (\text{virus-cell}),,ijl} \\
& + \mathbf{n}_{\text{radiated}}(\downarrow\downarrow), \text{ induced Virus,,ijl} \mathbf{S}_{\text{radiated}}(\downarrow\downarrow), \text{ induced Virus,,ijl}]] \\
& \otimes [\prod_{z=1..n} \cos\alpha_{1,noise} \dots \cos\alpha_{w,noise}] \times \\
& \otimes [\Sigma_{f_1=0,1} \tan^{f_1} \alpha_{1,noise}] \dots [\Sigma_{f=0,1} \tan^f \alpha_{w,noise}] \\
& \quad \frac{\otimes [\mathcal{N}\hbar]^2}{2 \mu_0} [\Sigma_m \mathbf{n}_{\text{sheet},m} \Sigma_n \mathbf{n}_{\text{bubble},mn} \\
& \quad \otimes [\Sigma_x [\mathbf{n}_{\uparrow\uparrow},mnx} \mathbf{S}'_{\uparrow\uparrow},mnx} \\
& \quad - \mathbf{n}_{\text{radiated}}(\uparrow\uparrow), (\text{virus-cell}),,mnx} \mathbf{S}'_{\text{radiated}}(\uparrow\uparrow), (\text{virus-cell}),,mnx} \\
& + \mathbf{n}_{\text{radiated}}(\uparrow\uparrow), \text{ induced Virus,,mnx} \mathbf{S}'_{\text{radiated}}(\uparrow\uparrow), \text{ induced Virus,,mnx}] \\
& \quad + \Sigma_y [\mathbf{n}_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny} \mathbf{S}'_{\downarrow\downarrow,mny} \\
& \quad - \mathbf{n}_{\text{radiated}}(\downarrow\downarrow), (\text{virus-cell}),mny} \mathbf{S}'_{\text{radiated}}(\downarrow\downarrow), (\text{virus-cell}),mny} \\
& + \mathbf{n}_{\text{radiated}}(\downarrow\downarrow), \text{ induced Virus,mny} \mathbf{S}'_{\text{radiated}}(\downarrow\downarrow), \text{ induced Virus,mny}]] \\
& \quad \otimes [\text{HSeparation Distance}]^{1/2}
\end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

From other side, total charges which move by this wave could be obtained from below equation:

$$Q_{\text{Virus-cell,bubbles}} = [[\Sigma_j \mathbf{n}_{\text{sheet},j} \Sigma_i \mathbf{n}_{\text{bubble},ij} [\Sigma_k \mathbf{n}_{\uparrow\uparrow},ijk$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \otimes [Q_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} - Q_{\text{radiated } (\uparrow\uparrow), (\text{virus-cell}),ijk} + Q_{\text{radiated } (\uparrow\uparrow), \text{induced Virus},ijk}] \\
& \quad + \sum_l n_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} \\
& \otimes [Q_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} - Q_{\text{radiated } (\downarrow\downarrow), (\text{virus-cell}),,ijl} + Q_{\text{radiated } (\downarrow\downarrow), , \text{induced Virus},,ijl}]] \\
& \quad + [\sum_m n_{\text{sheet},m} \sum_n n_{\text{bubble},mn} [\sum_x n_{\uparrow\uparrow, mnx} \\
& \otimes [Q'_{\uparrow\uparrow, mnx} - Q'_{\text{radiated } (\uparrow\uparrow), (\text{virus-cell}),mnx} + Q'_{\text{radiated } (\uparrow\uparrow), \text{induced Virus},mnx}] \\
& \quad + \sum_y n_{\downarrow\downarrow, mny} \\
& \otimes [Q'_{\downarrow\downarrow, mny} - Q'_{\text{radiated } (\downarrow\downarrow), (\text{virus-cell}),mny} + Q'_{\text{radiated } (\downarrow\downarrow), \text{induced Virus},mny}]]] + Q_{\text{noise}}]
\end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

Using equations (23) and (24), we obtain the below current density:

$$\begin{aligned}
& J_{\text{Virus-cell,bubbles}} \rightarrow \\
& Q_{\text{Virus-cell,bubbles}} V_{\text{Virus-cell,bubbles}} \rightarrow \\
& [[\sum_j n_{\text{sheet},j} \sum_i n_{\text{bubble},ij} [\sum_k n_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} \\
& \otimes [Q_{\uparrow\uparrow,ijk} - Q_{\text{radiated } (\uparrow\uparrow), (\text{virus-cell}),ijk} + Q_{\text{radiated } (\uparrow\uparrow), \text{induced Virus},ijk}] \\
& \quad + \sum_l n_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} \\
& \otimes [Q_{\downarrow\downarrow,ijl} - Q_{\text{radiated } (\downarrow\downarrow), (\text{virus-cell}),,ijl} + Q_{\text{radiated } (\downarrow\downarrow), , \text{induced Virus},,ijl}]] \\
& \quad + [\sum_m n_{\text{sheet},m} \sum_n n_{\text{bubble},mn} [\sum_x n_{\uparrow\uparrow, mnx} \\
& \otimes [Q'_{\uparrow\uparrow, mnx} - Q'_{\text{radiated } (\uparrow\uparrow), (\text{virus-cell}),mnx} + Q'_{\text{radiated } (\uparrow\uparrow), \text{induced Virus},mnx}]
\end{aligned}$$

$$+ \sum_y \mathbf{n}_{\downarrow\downarrow, mny}$$

$$\otimes [Q'_{\downarrow\downarrow, mny} - Q'_{\text{radiated } (\downarrow\downarrow), (\text{virus-cell}), mny} + Q'_{\text{radiated } (\downarrow\downarrow), \text{induced Virus}, mny}]] + Q_{\text{noise}}$$

$$\otimes [L_{\text{sheet-sheet}} [[\sum_j \mathbf{n}_{\text{sheet}, j} \sum_i \mathbf{n}_{\text{bubble}, ij} [\sum_k \mathbf{n}_{\uparrow\uparrow, ijk}$$

$$\otimes [\mathbf{m}_{\uparrow\uparrow, ijk} - \mathbf{m}_{\text{radiated } (\uparrow\uparrow), (\text{virus-cell}), ijk} + \mathbf{m}_{\text{radiated } (\uparrow\uparrow), \text{induced Virus}, ijk}]$$

$$+ \sum_l \mathbf{n}_{\downarrow\downarrow, ij l}]$$

$$\otimes [\mathbf{m}_{\downarrow\downarrow, ij l} - \mathbf{m}_{\text{radiated } (\downarrow\downarrow), (\text{virus-cell}), ij l} + \mathbf{m}_{\text{radiated } (\downarrow\downarrow), \text{induced Virus}, ij l}]]$$

$$+ [\sum_m \mathbf{n}_{\text{sheet}, m} \sum_n \mathbf{n}_{\text{bubble}, mn} [\sum_x \mathbf{n}_{\uparrow\uparrow, mnx}$$

$$\otimes [\mathbf{m}'_{\uparrow\uparrow, mnx} - \mathbf{m}'_{\text{radiated } (\uparrow\uparrow), (\text{virus-cell}), mnx} + \mathbf{m}'_{\text{radiated } (\uparrow\uparrow), \text{induced Virus}, mnx}]$$

$$+ \sum_y \mathbf{n}_{\downarrow\downarrow, mny}$$

$$\otimes [m'_{\downarrow\downarrow, mny} - m'_{\text{radiated } (\downarrow\downarrow), (\text{virus-cell}), mny} + m'_{\text{radiated } (\downarrow\downarrow), \text{induced Virus}, mny}]] + m_{\text{noise}}]^{-\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\otimes [[2\pi [\sum_j \mathbf{n}_{\text{sheet}, j} \sum_i \mathbf{n}_{\text{bubble}, ij} [\sum_j \mathbf{n}_{\text{sheet}, j}]$$

$$+ 2\pi [\sum_m \mathbf{n}_{\text{sheet}, m} \sum_i \mathbf{n}_{\text{bubble}, nm} [\sum_m \mathbf{n}_{\text{sheet}, m}]]$$

$$\frac{\otimes [\mathcal{N} \hbar]^2}{2 \mu_0} [\sum_j \mathbf{n}_{\text{sheet}, j} \sum_i \mathbf{n}_{\text{bubble}, ij} [\sum_k [\mathbf{n}_{\uparrow\uparrow, ijk} \mathbf{S}_{\uparrow\uparrow, ijk}$$

$$- \mathbf{n}_{\text{radiated } (\uparrow\uparrow), (\text{virus-cell}), ijk} \mathbf{S}_{\text{radiated } (\uparrow\uparrow), (\text{virus-cell}), ijk}]$$

$$+ \mathbf{n}_{\text{radiated } (\uparrow\uparrow), \text{induced Virus}, ijk} \mathbf{S}_{\text{radiated } (\uparrow\uparrow), \text{induced Virus}, ijk}]$$

$$+ \sum_l [\mathbf{n}_{\downarrow\downarrow, ij l} \mathbf{S}_{\downarrow\downarrow, ij l}]$$

$$- \mathbf{n}_{\text{radiated } (\downarrow\downarrow), (\text{virus-cell}), ij l} \mathbf{S}_{\text{radiated } (\downarrow\downarrow), (\text{virus-cell}), ij l}]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \mathbf{n} \text{ radiated } (\downarrow\downarrow), \text{ induced Virus},,ijl \mathbf{S} \text{ radiated } (\downarrow\downarrow), \text{ induced Virus},,ijl]]] \\
& \otimes [\prod_{z=1..n} \cos\alpha_{1,noise} \dots \dots \cos\alpha_{w,noise}] \times \\
& \otimes [\sum_{f_1=0,1} \tan^{f_1} \alpha_{1,noise}] \dots \dots [\sum_{f=0,1} \tan^f \alpha_{w,noise}] \\
& \frac{\otimes [N\hbar]^2}{2 \mu_0} [\sum_m n_{sheet,m} \sum_n n_{bubble,mn} \\
& \otimes [\sum_x [n_{\uparrow\uparrow},mnx} \mathbf{S}'_{\uparrow\uparrow},mnx} \\
& - \mathbf{n} \text{ radiated } (\uparrow\uparrow), \text{ (virus-cell)},,mnx} \mathbf{S}' \text{ radiated } (\uparrow\uparrow), \text{ (virus-cell)},,mnx} \\
& + \mathbf{n} \text{ radiated } (\uparrow\uparrow), \text{ induced Virus},,mnx} \mathbf{S}' \text{ radiated } (\uparrow\uparrow), \text{ induced Virus},,mnx}] \\
& + \sum_y [n_{\downarrow\downarrow},mny} \mathbf{S}'_{\downarrow\downarrow},mny} \\
& - \mathbf{n} \text{ radiated } (\downarrow\downarrow), \text{ (virus-cell)},,mny} \mathbf{S}' \text{ radiated } (\downarrow\downarrow), \text{ (virus-cell)},,mny} \\
& + \mathbf{n} \text{ radiated } (\downarrow\downarrow), \text{ induced Virus},,mny} \mathbf{S}' \text{ radiated } (\downarrow\downarrow), \text{ induced Virus},,mny]]] \\
& \otimes [H_{\text{Separation Distance}}]^{1/2}]
\end{aligned}$$

Above equation shows the current of bubbles which produce virtual Viruses around (virus-cell)s. These Viruses make some virtual connections with real viruses. These real viruses make a mistake in diagnosing other real Viruses with opposite spins and connect them. Consequently, real-virtual viral systems become confined within bubbles with opposite spin and viral effects disappear.

Conclusions:

One of main problems which occur during covid 19 disease is decreasing of needed oxygen molecules within the human's lungs. This may have many parallel reasons for example, applying

oxygen molecules in building non-desired matters by viruses. However, besides these reasons, one may guess that spinor interactions between viruses and oxygen triplets cause to repels of oxygen molecules and their reductions. Oxygen molecules have triplet states which means at least two spins of them are parallel to each other ($O-O(\uparrow\uparrow)$). On the other hand, viruses are built from many charges like electrons which have spins and it is natural that some viruses have special spins in some conditions. These spinning viruses could repel oxygen and other biological molecules with the same spins and attract any anti-parallel spinor. For example, spinors within alveolar cells of lungs are connected to blood molecules and hemoglobins and could take some spinning states from iron atoms within them. These spinors attract oxygen molecules and spinning viruses with opposite spins and repel similar spins. With respect to this point that spinors of viruses may be very more than oxygen molecules, these particles remain within the alveolus and oxygen molecules go out. We can use of these molecules in diagnosing selected spins by alveolar cells. We could put two connected vessels, one opens and includes water and oxygen molecules and other one is closed and includes viruses. We change temperature along this system from warm to cool and then warm again. During respirations, spinning molecules interact with molecules in this system and similar spinning molecules and viruses go away and anti-parallel spinors become close to the face. By changing temperatue, some spinor waves are exchanged between two vessels and some virtual spinning viruses are produced and confned within the water bubbles. These bubbles go out of open vessels and move towards the face. These bubbles could enter into alveolus and interact with real viruses. Spins of bubbles and real viruses are opposite and interact each other. Consequently, some spinless bubbles are emerged which have no effects on alveolar cells. One can use of this technique in designing a spinor mask. This mask contains water and oxygen molecules and viruses. During respirations, non-

effective viruses become close to the face and effective viruses go away and located on other side. These spinning viruses repel similar harmful viruses and prevent of their closing to the face.

We have formulate the model and obtained the frequencies and currents.

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